

Management development practices: Empirical evidence from Sri Lanka

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Citation:

Akuratiyagamage, V.M. (2006). Management development practices: Empirical evidence from Sri Lanka. The International Journal of Human Resource Management, 17(9), 1605–1623.

This Version is available at: doi: [10.1080/09585190600878451](https://doi.org/10.1080/09585190600878451)

Abstract

Being a South Asian developing country, management development (MD) practices in Sri Lanka has received insufficient attention. The paper reports results of an empirical investigation of 219 managers and seventy-eight human resource (HR) managers on MD practices in Sri Lanka. The study investigated different process by which MD takes place in organizations, the nature of immediate senior managers' support for MD, the importance given to the HRM function in the organizational strategy and the HR managers' contribution to the organizational strategy on MD aspects. The research findings indicate more similar MD practices across the three forms of ownership- local, foreign and joint venture. The conclusions address the existing practice and implications.

Key words: Human resource management; joint venture; management development; Sri Lanka.

INTRODUCTION

Being a component of human resource development (HRD), management development (MD) has been accepted as an important mean of developing managers to make the best use of resources. The Sri Lankan literature suggests that the introduction of open economic policies in 1977 made a significant impact on the realisation of the importance of HRD in the total organizational process (Central Bank of Sri Lanka, 2004; Chandratilake, 1997). On one hand, Sri Lankan government has been taking steps to enhance industry relevant employee skills to attract foreign direct investment. On the other hand, local entrepreneurs having recognized that human

resource (HR) gives organizations a competitive advantage over others even within the same industry have taken measures to organize HRD programmes in their organizations and to bring HR managers into corporate management. However, irrespective of encouraging signs of growing investment on and incidents of HRD, MD practices in Sri Lanka remains dubious due to lack of studies.

The focus of this paper is on the discussion of the results of an empirical investigation on what are the processes by which MD take place in organizations? Do immediate senior managers support MD? Do organizations give important place to the HRM function in the organizational strategy and what is human resource (HR) managers' contribution to the organizational strategy on MD aspects? To date there remains a dearth of empirical research conducted to address these in the Asian developing countries. Specifically, no such studies have been conducted in the context of Sri Lanka though there are sings of growing investment on HRD. Therefore, this paper seeks to answer the above questions by offering a brief description on the Sri Lankan context and then analysing the results of the survey conducted in three major forms of companies, i.e., local, foreign and joint venture in Sri Lanka. The conclusions address the existing practice and implications.

SRI LANKAN CONTEXT

Sri Lanka, which became independent in 1948, eventually followed the economic, political and administrative structures introduced by the British, which lasted over several centuries. At the time of regaining independence, Sri Lanka was mainly an agricultural economy. The production of and trade in three plantation crops, i.e., tea, rubber and coconut, contributed to a major share

of the national income. However, by the time of regaining independence, the economy was open to free trade and it was fully integrated to the global economic system with a considerable degree of external dependence (Central Bank of Sri Lanka, 1998). However, from mid 1960s the governments of Sri Lanka had gradually introduced array of controls to promote local industrial and agricultural activities as that was widely accepted at that time in many emerging economies (Central Bank of Sri Lanka, 1998). In 1977, far-reaching policy reforms had been introduced to shift the focus from an inward looking development strategy to an outward looking development strategy to free the economy from the array of controls (Central Bank of Sri Lanka, 1998). Since independence, the country has faced severe challenges in the sphere of industrialisation, like its other counterparts in the developing world. In the pursuit of industrialisation, Sri Lanka is left with few options to survive and thrive in a more complex and unpredictable global situation. By introducing open economic policies, in 1977, the governments have adopted an economic strategy designed to industrialise through foreign direct investment. With high unemployment and insufficient indigenous capital, the attraction of foreign investors becomes a major priority. On the other hand, in response to increasing global competition, lower labour cost in Sri Lanka and inducements from the Sri Lankan governments to the foreign capital, the number of international businesses coming into Sri Lanka has been increasing. Steady support from Asian Development Bank in financing public infrastructure projects and the establishment of numerous industrial parks and zones has also significantly affected the increase in the investments and also the performance of the manufacturing sector. In the mean time, the manufacturing sector has become the growth oriented sector by increasing its share in the overall production, total employment and export earnings of the country (Central Bank of Sri Lanka, 2004).

Sri Lanka first began to promote the clothing manufacturing industry during 1960s as an import substitution industry. However, the period after the late 1970s saw a rapid expansion in the export-oriented clothing manufacturing industry in Sri Lanka, with the introduction of market-oriented liberal economic policies in 1977. Given the easy separability of the clothing manufacturing into different stages, overseas manufacturers tend to relocate their production facilities to low production cost countries, such as Sri Lanka, without much difficulty. Hence, the overseas manufacturers of clothing from both East Asia (such as Hong Kong, Taiwan, South Korea and Singapore) and Europe (such as Germany and the U.K.) have relocated their production facilities to Sri Lanka and fuelled the growth of the Sri Lankan export-oriented clothing manufacturing industry. At present, several export-oriented clothing manufacturing companies operate in Sri Lanka as wholly local owned companies (local), wholly foreign owned companies (foreign) and local and foreign joint venture companies (joint venture). This industry has become the leading manufacturing and export industry in Sri Lanka by 1990s. It has emerged as the country's main export earner and the largest single employment provider in the industrial sector (Central Bank of Sri Lanka, 2004). Hence, policy makers have placed a heavy emphasis on the industry as a means of generating employment and foreign exchange earnings by recognizing it as the main contributor to overall economic development.

Board of Investment of Sri Lanka (BOI), which is the primary government authority responsible for identifying, promoting and facilitating both foreign and local investments in the country, classify export-oriented clothing manufacturing companies by ownership form as local, foreign and joint venture (BOI, 2000). At the time of the study there were 207 (eighty-two local, sixty-eight foreign and fifty-seven joint venture) export-oriented clothing manufacturing companies,

which were registered under BOI, operating in the country. By investment size, BOI classifies a company with the total project investment exceeding US\$ 8.0 million (or Sri Lankan Rupees 500 million) as a large scale project (BOI, 2000). However, BOI does not provide a “term” to describe the companies that does not come under large-scale projects. For the investigation, those companies have been named as “non-large scale projects”. Of the 207 companies, 200 companies came under the category of non-large scale projects.

MANAGEMENT DEVELOPMENT

Effective management is vital for organizational success. Organizations do not receive immediate returns on the time managers spend on MD, yet growth of the organizations demands upgrading of managerial skills (Lawler et al, 1995). MD in organizations is about development and change through learning giving emphasis on how, what and where individuals learn focusing on skills, knowledge and abilities that individuals need in order to operate and co-operate effectively in an organizational context. On the other hand, the provision of MD increases the level of commitment of managers to the organization and their perceptions that the organization is a good place to work. Hence, MD provided by organizations indicates commitment to develop managers while the recipients feel valued.

The literature suggests two distinct processes of MD- informal and formal (Marsick and Watkins, 1997; Mole, 2000; Mumford, 1997). Informal processes usually occur during the course of managers’ everyday work. Thus, these are by products of daily work activities such as, task accomplishment, trial and error experimentation, or interpersonal interactions and managers

may not set out intentionally and explicitly to learn something through pre-planned means (Marsick and Watkins 1997; Mumford 1997; Woodall, 2000). However, meeting organizational challenges leave little choice but to absorb lessons from the experience and develop new skills/abilities. Therefore, informal learning has to be deliberately encouraged by an organization (Woodall, 2000). Formal processes, on the other hand, include institutionally sponsored, planned and deliberate processes. These are often monitored and controlled by people other than the individual managers involved (Marsick and Watkins, 1997; Mumford, 1997), such as job rotation, coaching and projects assignments. Though none of the processes are superior to others, it is important to select different and appropriate processes rather than be wedded to a single one (Huczynski, 1983; Wills 1998a). Further, as managers differ in their preferred approach to learning, some may enjoy learning from informal incidences while others may not. Therefore, a balanced view of MD should include both formal and informal processes (Marsick and Watkins, 1997; Mole, 2000; Mumford, 1997; Woodall, 2000).

When the provision of MD is viewed as a long-term investment, organizations should provide encouragement, guidance and opportunities for development (Megginson and Whitaker, 1997; Mumford, 1997; Woodall, 2000). If an organization minimises the importance of people for its' overall success, so will the members in the senior managerial posts. Several means could be used to encourage MD in an organization, such as encouraging managers to identify their own development needs, providing feedback on performance and achieved learning, and assisting managers to identify learning opportunities on the job (Mumford, 1997). On the other hand, there are several unwritten and unspoken channels that could be used to influence the status of MD in

an organization, such as frequency of in-company MD programmes are postponed or cancelled because of other organizational engagements (Wills, 1998b).

Above all, there are specific contributions that the HRM function can make in the corporate strategy in connection to MD (Budhwar and Sparrow, 1997; Hsu and Leat, 2000). The HRM function can provide input concerning the availability of the required managerial talent (quantity, quality, and skill mix) and the costs of acquiring, retaining, developing, and motivating it. HRM strategy should, therefore, be driven by the assessment of skill requirements and skill deficits, since these could frame the possibilities for an organization (Hendry, 1995). However, whilst a number of functions influence organizational strategic decisions, the HRM function exercised the least influence (Budhwar and Sparrow, 1997). Further, though organizations have a range of HRM policies these usually have little interconnection between them and little interconnection with strategic decisions (Storey and Sisson, 1993). On the other hand, though strategic planners identify the need of more HR information in the strategic decisions few have successfully carved out an appropriate role for their HRM function (Megginson et al, 2004). In this context, HR managers have a vital role to play. The ability of the HR managers to add value in determining the strategic direction of the organization with a particular focus on MD is important (Borucki and Lafley, 1984). They have to be active in the strategic decision-making - they should participate in the strategic decision-making; they should make suggestions relating to human resources; organizations should take into account their suggestions and be included in the strategic decisions. However, Budhwar and Sparrow (1997) revealed inadequate representation of HR managers at the Board level, in India; Downie and Coates (1994) revealed that Canadian HR managers were often outside the decision-making circle. In this context, the degree of

participation of HR managers at the strategic level mainly depends on the extent to which top management is willing to share decision-making (Devanna et al, 1984; Mumford, 1997).

ANALYTICAL FRAMEWORK

The main focus of the study was to investigate the following dimensions of MD.

The processes by which MD takes place in organizations

This was directed to address both formal and informal processes. Formal processes were divided into four main categories, i.e., job redesign processes, processes within the job, processes external to the job, and self-development processes (Mumford, 1997). Job redesign processes were further classified into job rotation, adding more responsibilities, special projects, and assignments in committees/task groups. Processes within the job were further classified into coaching, counselling, mentoring and action learning. Processes external to the job were further classified into in-company programmes, external courses such as, Diploma and MBA, attendance at seminars/conferences, and distance learning. Self-development processes were further classified into reading and guided reflection. Informal processes were classified into learning from doing the job, learning from handling problems on the job, learning from company meetings, learning from business visits, learning from social occasions related to work, learning from feedback given by superiors, and learning from observing colleagues/superiors (Mumford, 1997; Cunningham, 1999).

The immediate senior managers' support for MD

This was directed to cover two dimensions. The first, the types of management positions exist in the companies and the composition of management (only foreigners, only locals, or a mix of foreigners and locals). The second, the way immediate senior managers facilitate managers to learn in terms of resources committed for MD i.e., time availability, budgetary allocations, and library facilities provided. And other means that they use to influence MD, i.e., encouragement given to take part in MD programmes, number of development opportunities provided, whether managers are prevented from undertaking MD programmes because of other organizational engagements, whether MD programmes are provided before being given promotions and whether managers are rewarded for their dedication to develop themselves (Wills, 1998b).

The importance given to the HRM function and HR managers' contribution to the organizational strategy on MD aspects

This was directed to address five dimensions. First, the existence of separate HR departments/units. Second, the importance given to the HRM function in the organizational strategy. Third, the existence of MD policies along with other HRM policies, i.e., policies to promote within the company, provide MD programmes before being given promotions, provide MD programmes based on continuous appraisal of performance, allocate certain number of hours for MD programmes each year, provide MD programmes before being given salary increments, and to move cross functionally (Hall, 1984; Mumford, 1997). Fourth, HR managers' contribution

to the organizational strategy on MD aspects. Finally, the existence of separate HRD units/departments.

As companies belong to three forms of ownership (local, foreign and joint venture) exist in the export-oriented clothing manufacturing industry in Sri Lanka, the study sought to further examine whether there are any significant differences in relation to the above dimensions of MD across the companies of the different forms of ownership.

METHOD

Population and sample

The export-oriented clothing manufacturing companies registered under BOI served as the population of the study. The list of the total population and its characteristics were provided by Research and Documentation Unit of BOI. At the time of the study there were 207 companies (eighty-two local, sixty-eight foreign, fifty-seven joint venture) registered under BOI, operating in the country. It was decided to select a proportionate stratified random sample of 100 companies (forty local, thirty-three foreign, twenty-seven joint venture) for the study. Simple random sampling method was used in drawing the desired number of elements from each stratum (local, foreign, joint venture). However, for various reasons the total number of companies that agreed to participate in the study amounted to seventy-eight (thirty-two local, twenty-six foreign, twenty joint venture). Of the companies that responded to the study, 41 per cent were locally owned; 33 percent were foreign owned. Fifty-nine per cent of the companies employed more

than ten managers and 26 per cent employed six to ten managers. Forty-six per cent had 101 to 500 employees, 33 per cent had 501 to 1000 employees, and 18 per cent had more than 1000 employees.

In the study, two different perspectives were probed using two sets of sample units- HR managers and managers of the companies- as there are disadvantages of collecting survey data from one source (Ichniowski et al, 1996; Nichols, 1986). From the seventy-eight companies that agreed to participate in the survey, all seventy-eight HR managers responded to the questionnaire (thirty-two local, twenty-six foreign, twenty joint venture). In selecting a sample of managers, initial contacts were made with four managers who were not working in the same managerial function in the seventy-eight companies (4x78), using simple random sample method. The total number of responses obtained amounted to 219 (104 local, sixty-five foreign, fifty joint venture). Eighteen HR managers (seven local, six foreign, five joint venture) and twenty-five managers (ten local, eight foreign, seven joint venture) from the stratified randomly selected sample willingly agreed to participate in the interviews.

With regard to demographics of the HR managers' sample, 64 per cent had professional qualifications. Nine per cent had postgraduate degrees, 36 per cent had degrees and 55 per cent had diploma as their highest educational qualification. With regard to years of service in the present company, 41 per cent had less than five years, 47 per cent had six to ten years, and 12 per cent had more than ten years of service in the present company. With regard to demographics of the managers' sample, 53 per cent were below thirty years old, 36 per cent were between thirty-one to forty years, 8 per cent were between forty-one to fifty years, and 3 per cent were more

than fifty years old. Seventy-six per cent had professional qualifications. Three per cent had postgraduate degrees; 40 per cent had degrees; 25 per cent had diploma; 31 per cent had General Certificate in Education (G.C.E.) (Advanced Level) and 1 per cent had G.C.E. (Ordinary Level) as their highest educational qualification. With regard to the years of service in the present company, 77 per cent had less than five years, 20 per cent had six to ten years, and 3 per cent had more than ten years of service in the present company. With regard to the level of management of the responding managers, lower level - 29 per cent; middle level - 45 per cent; senior level - 21 per cent; management advisor/staff specialist- 5 per cent. The functional distribution of the managers consisted of: production- 25 per cent; marketing/merchandising- 20 per cent; business planning- 16 per cent; accounting and finance-12 per cent; information technology-10 per cent; purchasing and stores-7 per cent; HR/labour relations-6 per cent; maintenance- 4 per cent.

Methods of data collection

The data was collected through survey questionnaires and interviews in order to capture the dimensions of the investigation. It is anticipated that the results of the questionnaire survey may provide access to breadth of experience while the interviews may provide depth by adding insight and substance to the questionnaire survey. Two questionnaires targeting HR managers and managers were constructed by the researcher who was unable to find any study conducted in Sri Lanka that had slight resemblance to this study. The preliminary investigations of the researcher gave insight into the HR practices within the industry. To collect necessary information in a manner that put the least burden on the respondents, information that could be accessible from other sources, such as interviews, was excluded from the self-administered

questionnaires. Most of the questions took the form of closed ended questions with responses on a Likert-scale as these have proven themselves to be more efficient and ultimately more reliable.

The survey questionnaire targeting HR managers covered:

- Importance given to the HR function in the organizational strategy process- invited the respondent to indicate using a five-point Likert scale ranging from (1) 'very low' to (5) 'very high';
- Existence of MD policies along with company's other HRM policies- invited the respondent to indicate other HRM policies by simply ticking the HRM policy areas applicable. An item labelled "other" was added to the list to enable respondent to state any HRM policy area that exist in his/her company, which was not offered by the questionnaire;
- HR managers' contribution to organizational strategy on MD aspects- invited the respondents to indicate using a five-point Likert scale ranging from (1) 'very low' to (5) 'very high';
- Existence of HRD units/departments- invited the respondent to indicate whether HRD unit/department exist in his/her company by simply circling a "yes/no" option;
- The way HR managers facilitate managers to learn- listed a range of ways that HR managers can facilitate inviting the respondent to indicate the frequently used avenues using a five-point Likert scale ranging from (1) 'never' to (5) 'always'. An item labelled

“other” was added to the list to enable respondent to state any other avenue that HR managers use to facilitate managers to learn in his/her company, which was not offered by the questionnaire;

- Management positions that exist in the companies- listed a range of managerial positions generally exist in the companies inviting the respondent to tick the managerial positions applicable. A tick box labelled “other” was added to the list to enable respondents to state any managerial position that exist in his/her company, which was not offered by the questionnaire; and
- Composition of management- listed a range of managerial positions generally exist in the companies inviting the respondent to tick whether these managerial positions are occupied by only foreigners, only locals, or a mix of foreigners and locals. A tick box labelled “other” was added to the list to enable respondent to state any managerial position that exist in his/her company, which was not offered by the questionnaire.

The survey questionnaire targeting managers covered:

- MD processes- listed a range of formal and informal processes sponsored by the companies inviting the respondent to indicate the frequently used processes using a five-point Likert scale ranging from (1) ‘never’ to (5) ‘always’ A tick box labelled “other” was added to the list to enable respondent to state any formal/informal process that exist in his/her company, which was not offered by the questionnaire; and

- The way immediate senior managers support MD- listed a range of options that address both resources committed for MD and other means of support for MD inviting the respondent to indicate how frequently those were exercised using a five-point Likert scale ranging from (1) 'never' to (5) 'always'. A tick box labelled "other" was added to the list to enable respondent to state any other that exist in connection to these items in his/her company, which was not offered by the questionnaire.

The both questionnaires were pilot-tested to improve the reliability and face validity of the instruments. For the pilot survey eight HR managers and twelve managers from the local, foreign and joint venture companies participated.

Interviews were deemed necessary to complement the survey questionnaires to corroborate the information that had been gathered from the survey questionnaires and to elaborate the field by exploring a greater variety of experiences offered by managers and HR managers. It was decided to conduct interviews after the preliminary analysis of data obtained from self-administered questionnaires for two reasons. First, the answers to the survey questionnaires may provide some new insights, which should be further investigated. Second, if the researcher discovered something that should have been asked but was omitted in the questionnaires, then those areas can be dealt with during the interviews. The interviews were structured along the main outline topics that were covered in the questionnaires but with open questions to explore those in more detail.

Methods of data analysis

Data analysis was conducted using the SPSS programme. In addition to descriptive statistics, one way between-subjects analysis of variance (ANOVA) or chi-square test was used appropriately to investigate the impact of ownership form. HR managers' and managers' comments on MD practices prevailing in the industry were categorised and incorporated into the discussion of the survey results.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

MD processes

The results of the formal MD processes are shown in table 1. As shown in table 1, job redesign processes are the most popular ($X=2.902$) followed by processes within the job ($x=2.639$). The least popular is self-development processes ($x=1.886$).

INSERT TABLE 1 ABOUT HERE

Table 1 also displays mean and ANOVA values by ownership. The results of ANOVA indicate that the impact of ownership is not significant in managers receiving job redesign processes, development processes within the job and development processes external to the job. However, there are significant differences across companies in managers' experiencing self-development

processes sponsored by the companies. Further analysis of Least Significant Differences (LSD) shows that managers from both foreign and joint venture companies are more likely to experience self-development processes provided by the companies than that of managers from the local companies.

Formal processes were analysed in detail through questionnaire survey and interviews. Detailed analysis of formal processes based on questionnaire survey is shown in table 2.

INSERT TABLE 2 ABOUT HERE

The majority of managers have experienced adding more responsibilities to learn as a job redesign process ($\bar{x}= 3.463$). Job rotation is also used in the companies ($\bar{x}=2.336$). However, it is revealed that job rotation is mainly used for the managers in the lower management level of the production function. None of the companies use this method to develop competent generalists or as a kind of horizontal fast track promotion mechanism for potential high flyers. Companies are unable to provide wide range of experience by planning movement between functions, between products or between countries. Further, it is explicit that Sri Lankan managerial labour market, like U.K. (Storey et al, 1997), is highly segmented. A manager begins his/her career in a function, which has its own professional body, entry qualifications, codes of ethics and discipline. Therefore, opportunities for managers to acquire experience from promotion and mobility within an organization rather than from moving between different organizations, is

limited. Attending at seminars and conferences ($x=3.088$) is also popular as a development process external to the job (ranked 2nd). However, attendance at external courses was ranked 10th ($x=2.421$). When these results are compared with other studies, these are not consistent with Lawler et al's (1995) observations in Thailand and Storey et al's (1997) observations in Britain as they revealed that formal processes to a greater extent rely on "courses" provided by outside vendors. However, the findings are consistent with Henderson et al's (2000) and Avery et al's (1999) findings as they also revealed that attendance in short courses or seminars on specific topics has often been experienced by managers. Though Institute of Management (1994) observed a trend towards a greater preference for coaches and mentors, in this study, those are not highly ranked (5th and 6th respectively). Mentoring ($x=2.751$), action learning ($x=2.734$) and coaching ($x=2.671$) obtained low mean values. None of the companies use open office plan at managerial levels that allow managers to observe their superiors, especially, when they work under stress, which is an invaluable within the job development experience for them. Distance learning is the least experienced process ($x=1.822$). Reading ($x=1.99$) and guided reflection ($x=1.925$) also received low responses. Though most of the managers have professional qualifications in their fields (76%), only 36 percent of them subscribe to magazines related to the profession or industry they attached to, by themselves. Thus, the pursuit of learning by reading is not a habit among managers in the industry. Interview responses indicated little facilitation of personal development plans and scant use of learning logs, diaries, etc. However, the results grouped under the three forms of ownership indicate that the impact of ownership is not significant in all the formal processes shown in table 2, except in the facilitation of guided reflection. Further analysis of LSD indicates that managers from both foreign and joint venture

companies are more likely to be facilitated with this than that of managers from local companies. This might lead to identify significant differences in self-development processes in table 1.

The results of the informal MD processes that provide learning opportunities for managers are shown in table 3.

INSERT TABLE 3 ABOUT HERE

As shown in table 3, learning from handling problems on the job ($X=4.226$), learning from doing the job ($x=4.225$), learning from observing colleagues/superiors ($x=3.747$) and learning from feedback given by superiors ($x=3.644$) are the most popular. Interviews with managers led to find that they learn most important lessons in their work lives, when they struggle between task accomplishment and chaos. Some managers are clearly able with hindsight to recognise the development value of those to them. Sharing experience within a company is common. However, though managers in senior levels are able to pass their experience to juniors, they don't have many opportunities to learn from others' experience. Learning from the incidences shown in table 3 involves active thinking about the importance of the experience and generalising it to apply when similar situations are encountered. However, all managers may not be capable of handling such incidences alone, they may need some help and feedback to reflect and plan for future incidences (Marsick and Watkins, 1997). Therefore, to investigate how far HR managers involve in facilitating managers to learn from such incidences, a question was included in the

questionnaire. However, all most all HR managers have not responded to that question. Hence, during the interviews with HR managers, it was inquired, again. The most of the HR managers revealed that though they accept the fact that managers learn lot from daily organizational experiences, their involvement in facilitating and deliberately encouraging managers to learn from them is rare or non-existent. Unlike Japan (Kagono, 1996), companies have not given much emphasis on formalising such experiences and this situation is not in line with the current trends in HRD (Cunningham, 1999; Mumford, 1997). As shown in table 3, further analysis of ANOVA indicates that the impact of ownership is not significant in 6 out of 7 items. However, there are significant differences in learning from social occasions related to work. Further analysis of LSD shows that managers from foreign companies are more likely to learn from social occasions related to work than that of managers from both joint venture and local companies.

Immediate senior managers' support

The results for the types of management positions exist in the companies and the composition of management are shown in appendix 1 and 2. As shown in appendix 1, director(s), production manager, finance manager and HR manager positions are common in the industry. Appendix 2 shows the composition of management - whether people in the positions are only locals, only foreigners or a mixture of locals and foreigners. All most all management positions of the local companies are held by the locals. In the joint venture companies, the involvement of foreign investment partners is at the very highest level of the companies, i.e., at the Board level sharing director(s) posts with the locals. In contrast to the situation of local and joint venture companies, in the foreign companies all the director positions and most of the senior management positions

are held by the foreigners. However, in all the companies, all the HR manager positions are held by the locals. Further, in all the companies, all the middle level management and lower level management positions are held by the locals.

The results for the immediate senior managers' support for MD are shown in table 4.

INSERT TABLE 4 ABOUT HERE

As shown in table 4, respondents are most satisfied with budgetary allocations ($x=3.10$).

Companies fully sponsor MD programmes that are identified through the development needs identification. Some companies also sponsor (fully or partly) MD programmes that are requested by managers themselves. Respondents are least satisfied with the library facilities provided ($x=2.142$). Table 2 also revealed that reading is not popular. However, some managers mentioned that their immediate superiors provide them with material to read if content is relevant to the interests of the companies. Time availability obtained a mean value of 3.055. Interviews with HR managers revealed that it is not difficult to get managers release to attend off-the-job MD programmes, such as seminars and workshops, organised by external institutions as few managers from a department/section attend them, at one time. However, HR managers find difficulties in getting managers released when organising in-company off-the-job programmes to fulfil development needs of several managers throughout the company.

The results for unwritten and unspoken channels used to influence the status of MD within an organization are also shown in table 4. According to the table, respondents are most satisfied with the number of development opportunities received since they have joined the company ($x=3.436$) and the encouragement they received for their development ($x=3.301$) than the rest of the items considered under other means of support. The prevention of managers from undergoing development opportunities because of other company engagements obtained a mean value of 2.723. The managers revealed that they have been provided with development opportunities to reach the required level of performance before being given promotions ($x=2.888$); they have received either monetary or non-monetary rewards for their dedication to develop themselves ($x=2.95$). The findings suggest that managers had experienced a support, which they perceived as helpful. As shown in table 4, further analysis of ANOVA indicates that the impact of ownership is not significant in all the items investigated.

The importance given to the HRM function and HR managers' contribution to the organizational strategy on MD aspects

For the existence of separate HR departments/units, the survey results indicated that all 78 companies have separate HR department/unit in their companies.

Table 5 shows the results for the importance given to the HRM function in the organizational strategy. The result of the analysis of ANOVA shown in table 5 does not indicate any impact of ownership. Though findings do not indicate very high level of importance given to the HRM

function, with the globalisation of business, the need of improving company status would become imperative for the survival of clothing manufacturing companies. Hence, the status of the HRM function in a company could be expected to improve further.

INSERT TABLE 5 ABOUT HERE

With regard to the existence of MD policies along with other HRM policies, primary investigations revealed that HRM policies specifying MD is rare in the industry. However, HRM policies specifying HRD is common in the industry. As shown in table 6, companies have specific HR policies on providing HRD programmes based on continuous appraisal of performance (99%), on providing development programmes before being given promotions (95%), on providing development programmes before being given salary increments (86%), and on promoting within the company (80%). However, further investigations revealed that, in many cases, “promotion within” policy is espoused and widely implemented for the managers in the lower level managerial posts; managers in the senior and middle level managerial posts are excluded. Therefore, in the companies that expressed high preference for externally recruited senior and middle managers, strong recruitment and remuneration function and a relatively weak development function for them have been seen. Although evidence indicates that it is common to have policies on moving managers cross-functionally and allocating certain number of hours for development programmes each year (Hall, 1984; Storey et al, 1997; Handy, 1987), the data from this investigation indicate that these are not common. Only 38 per cent of the companies have

HR policies on moving cross-functionally and 29 per cent of the companies have HR policies on allocating certain number of hours for development programmes each year. Further, as shown in table 6, the impact of ownership is significant in item 4, i.e., allocating certain number of hours for development programmes each year. Though 70 per cent of joint venture companies allocate certain number of hours for development programmes each year, this percentage is low for local (16%) and foreign (12%) companies.

INSERT TABLE 6 ABOUT HERE

However, investigations revealed that HRD policies specifying MD are rare or virtually non-existing in the responding companies. Formal written statements about directions and content of MD seemed not to exist in a single coherent document. This implies a considerable degree of scope and opportunity for the HR managers to develop a strategic dimension to their role.

However, this situation is not a surprise as Hsu and Leat (2000) in the Taiwan context, Budhwar and Sparrow (1997) in the Indian and Thailand context and Mumford et al (1987), and Mabey and Thomson (2000) in the U.K. context also observed that a considerable number of companies affirmed to have unwritten HRD/HRM policies.

There were 3 questions related to HR managers' contribution to the organizational strategy on MD/HRD aspects in the survey. As shown in table 7, the results of the analysis revealed that the HR managers participate in the company decision-making ($x=3.628$), contribute to company

decision-making ($x=3.321$) and their suggestions are accepted at the Board Level ($x=3.308$). Most of the HR managers involved in the development of the corporate strategy from the outset; they have been involved in company extension programmes. Thus, these observations are in line with Borucki and Lafley (1984), Devanna et al (1984), and Mumford (1997). However, in few companies, HR managers played a role that is more operational than strategic- their role is fully subservient to the business strategy- and business strategies ultimately determine the HR policies and practices. According to table 7, though the HR managers' contribution does not vary across companies of different ownership, the mean values do not show very high contribution; their contribution has to be further improved. It could be suggested that companies have to carve out an appropriate role for their HR function/manager; HR managers should be active within the decision-making circle.

INSERT TABLE 7 ABOUT HERE

Finally, a question on the existence of separate HRD units/departments was also included in the survey. The results revealed that 52 per cent of the companies have separate HRD units/departments in their companies. Further analysis of chi-square indicates that the impact of ownership is significant (Sig: 0.04). The results of the analysis revealed that fewer local companies (47%) and foreign companies (39%) have separate HRD units/departments than that of joint venture companies (75%). Though all 78 companies have HR departments, just more than half of the companies have HRD units/departments. This shows that companies have to

curve out a specific place for HRD in the organizations. In this connection, Arthur et al (1995) and Hsu and Leat (2000) also revealed the importance of having a separate units/departments for HRD. However, in Japan, particular weight was given to the departmental heads and individual managers when it comes to MD, and had given little emphasis on separate and special HRD department (Storey et al, 1997).

CONCLUSIONS

This paper has based on an empirical investigation into MD practices in Sri Lanka. The design of the study made it possible to generalise some of the findings in a broader perspective. Therefore, the findings have theoretical and practical implications for the MD practices in Sri Lanka.

Managers regarded daily organizational experiences as one of the best ways of learning. At the same time, they may need some help and feedback to reflect and plan for future incidences.

Though most of the HR managers revealed that they accept the fact that managers learn lot from experience, their involvement in facilitating managers to take the best use of informal processes attached to daily organizational experiences and deliberately encouraging managers to learn from them are not at high level. This situation emphasises the need of finding ways for formalising experience gained from daily organizational life and developing an environment conducive to such learning.

MD policies express company's commitment to continuous development of managers. If companies had specific written MD policies, they would have given a high degree of importance

to MD in the corporate strategy. As the industry itself is built on short-term profits and due to easy separability of the manufacturing process into different stages, investors (foreign and local) are able to disintegrate their production lines into low production cost countries, without much difficulty when profits decrease. In this context, they may not be prepared to spend sufficient time to develop appropriate MD practices in Sri Lanka. In such a situation, investors' preferred managerial practices could have been tailored to meet business objectives conditioned by the global competitive environment. Such an orientation allows too little time to wait for the benefits of HRD, MD in particular. Therefore, HRD has a short time horizon. This could drive out long-term MD investment at the workplace and "destroy" the basis of MD as a part of the corporate strategy. However, it is also possible to argue that even though HRD has a short-term focus, it can still offer to improve or enable managers' to learn skills, knowledge and abilities that are needed to perform his/her present job or any other jobs of the organization.

MD should balance the interests of organizations as well as managers and should provide managers opportunities to enhance and realise their potential and advance in their careers, which increase their perception that the organization is a good place to work. In this context, the HR managers' contribution has to be further improved. Though few companies have successfully carved out an appropriate role for their HRM function, the actual status and the contribution of the HR function/manager have to be sought within their own organizations. Therefore, there is a need to understand the importance and constraints on the HRM function/manager within a wider organizational framework.

It is evident from the results of ANOVA that all companies are more similar in the provision of MD, irrespective of the ownership form. This situation shows that though foreign investors/foreign joint venture partners do bring their ideas, local companies are not alien to them. As Kerr et al (1960) argued, industrialisation would ensure that managerial attitudes, values and behaviours could become increasingly uniform. One can argue that the Sri Lankan management practices are currently undergoing a rapid process of grafting practices that come into the play in several forms. First, though it is not compulsory, export-oriented clothing manufacturers identify international standards of certification as a source of competitive advantage, especially, to compete with recently entered countries to the industry. In many cases, the first step organizations take towards developing formal HRD programmes is to abide by ISO 9000 standards. Though international standards do not specify requirements of MD, international standards have resulted in a growing awareness about HRD and led to more universal HRD practices. Second, technological assistance programmes seems to have an impact on Sri Lanka that encouraged rapid technological and educational advancement primarily via skills or knowledge transfer. Finally, international businesses operate in the export-oriented clothing manufacturing industry as wholly foreign owned and foreign/local joint ventures for more than 25 years; wholly local owned companies are in competition with them to attract newly passed out graduates and professional managers from the labour market. In this context, local companies may seek to modify features of their organizational environment to suit foreign and joint venture MD practices. Hence, one can argue that foreign and joint venture companies eventually influenced and modified the management practices in Sri Lanka. All of these may influence to have more similar MD practices across companies of different ownership revealing Sri Lanka is not detached from the rest of the world.

However, Hofstede (1993) has shown that concepts of HRM and HRD might be both countries specific and argued that the concept of HRD would never have been invented in Asia; it came as a foreign idea, to be adapted to the different local situations. The studies of more quantitative in nature do not allow in depth analysis. Therefore, there is a need of further in depth case studies of comparative analysis in furthering the understanding.

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TABLES

Table 1: Formal MD processes

Item	Overall <i>Mean</i> (<i>SD</i>)	Local <i>Mean</i> (<i>SD</i>)	Foreign <i>Mean</i> (<i>SD</i>)	Joint venture <i>Mean</i> (<i>SD</i>)	ANOVA	
					F	Sig.
Job redesign processes	2.902 (1.000)	2.912 (1.043)	2.926 (.970)	2.85 (.967)	.092	.912
Processes within job	2.639 (1.063)	2.59 (1.102)	2.658 (1.029)	2.715 (1.041)	.241	.786
Processes external to job	2.422 (1.422)	2.319 (1.848)	2.465 (.948)	2.555 (.943)	.531	.589
Self-development processes	1.886 (1.243)	1.649 (1.425)	2.092 (1.018)	2.11 (1.011)	3.682	.027

Note: p < 0.05

Table 2: Detailed breakdown of formal MD processes

Item	Overall Mean (SD)	Local Mean (SD)	Foreign Mean (SD)	Joint venture Mean (SD)	ANOVA	
					F	Sig.
<i>Job redesign methods</i>						
Job rotation	2.336 (1.338)	2.576 (1.436)	2.154 (1.214)	2.10 (1.233)	3.022	.051
Given more responsibilities to learn	3.463 (1.192)	3.465 (1.136)	3.477 (1.226)	3.44 (1.28)	.014	.986
Work in special projects	3.004 (1.288)	3.01 (1.292)	3.077 (1.302)	2.90 (1.281)	.266	.767
Assignments in committees/task groups	2.916 (1.322)	2.84 (1.361)	3.00 (1.262)	2.96 (1.339)	.322	.725
<i>Development processes within the job</i>						
Coaching	2.671 (1.245)	2.653 (1.301)	2.584 (1.088)	2.82 (1.335)	.522	.594
Counselling	2.516 (1.27)	2.525 (1.308)	2.446 (1.25)	2.592 (1.24)	.186	.83
Mentoring	2.751 (1.341)	2.794 (1.388)	2.708 (1.388)	2.72 (1.195)	.099	.906
Action learning	2.734 (1.271)	2.57 (1.249)	2.892 (1.312)	2.86 (1.245)	1.59	.206
<i>Development processes external to the job</i>						
In-company programmes	2.83 (1.295)	2.882 (1.26)	2.692 (1.391)	2.9 (1.249)	.521	.595
External courses such as Diploma and MBA	2.421 (1.351)	2.455 (1.36)	2.4 (1.378)	2.38 (1.323)	.063	.939
Attendance at seminars/conferences	3.088 (1.267)	3.118 (1.291)	3.015 (1.243)	3.122 (1.268)	.152	.86
Distance learning	1.822 (1.032)	1.788 (1.062)	1.83 (.993)	1.88 (1.042)	.134	.875
<i>Self-development methods</i>						
Reading	1.99 (1.182)	1.902 (1.181)	2.015 (1.165)	2.14 (1.21)	.698	.499
Guided reflection	1.925 (1.238)	1.686 (1.094)	2.169 (1.387)	2.08 (1.242)	3.568	.03

Note: $p < 0.05$

Table 3: Informal development processes

Item	Overall Mean (SD)	Local Mean (SD)	Foreign Mean (SD)	Joint venture Mean (SD)	ANOVA	
					F	Sig.
Learn from doing the job	4.225 (.803)	4.301 (.777)	4.169 (.782)	4.14 (.88)	.897	.409
Learn from handling problems on the job	4.226 (.751)	4.252 (.723)	4.215 (.78)	4.184 (.781)	.147	.864
Learn from company meetings	3.498 (1.08)	3.461 (1.122)	3.585 (1.073)	3.458 (1.009)	.300	.741
Learn from business visits	3.357 (1.329)	3.414 (1.355)	3.385 (1.258)	3.204 (1.384)	.427	.653
Learn from social occasions related to work	3.234 (1.147)	3.1 (1.283)	3.539 (.936)	3.102 (1.045)	3.37	.036
Learn from the feedback given by superiors	3.644 (1.094)	3.559 (1.139)	3.708 (1.056)	3.735 (1.056)	.585	.558
Learn from observing colleagues/superiors	3.747 (.969)	3.696 (1.097)	3.892 (.831)	3.666 (.847)	1.07	.334

Note: $p < 0.05$

Table 4: Immediate senior managers' support

Item	Overall Mean (SD)	Local Mean (SD)	Foreign Mean (SD)	Joint venture Mean (SD)	ANOVA	
					F	Sig.
Resources committed for MD						
Time available	3.055 (1.115)	3.09 (1.186)	3.02 (1.067)	3.02 (1.039)	.135	.874
Budgetary allocations	3.10 (1.153)	2.89 (1.173)	3.08 (1.094)	3.12 (1.189)	.851	.428
Library facilities	2.142 (1.185)	1.94 (1.059)	2.29 (1.295)	2.36 (1.241)	2.89	.058
Other means of support for MD						
Satisfaction regarding number of development opportunities received	3.436 (1.126)	3.49 (1.170)	3.28 (1.125)	3.54 (1.034)	.959	.385
Encourage development	3.301 (1.2)	3.25 (1.236)	3.22 (1.192)	3.52 (1.129)	1.092	.337
Prevented from undertaking development opportunities	2.722 (1.226)	2.817 (1.26)	2.569 (1.224)	2.72 (1.161)	.817	.443
Developed before promotion	2.888 (1.109)	2.922 (1.168)	2.651 (1.018)	3.122 (1.053)	2.623	.075
Managers are rewarded	2.95 (1.193)	3 (1.165)	2.89 (1.251)	2.92 (1.192)	.182	.834

Note: $p < 0.05$

Table 5: Importance given to the HRM function in the organizational strategy process

Item	Overall <i>Mean</i> (<i>SD</i>)	Local <i>Mean</i> (<i>SD</i>)	Foreign <i>Mean</i> (<i>SD</i>)	Joint venture <i>Mean</i> (<i>SD</i>)	ANOVA	
					F	Sig.
Importance given to the HRM function	3.115 (1.056)	3.16 (1.167)	2.96 (1.182)	3.25 (.638)	.455	.636

Note: $p < 0.05$

Table 6: Existence of HRD policies in harmony with company's other HRM policies

Item	Overall	Local	Foreign	Joint venture	Chi-square	
					Value	Sig.
Promote within the company	80%	81%	73%	85%	1.04	.594
Provide development programmes before being given promotions	95%	88%	100%	100%	5.933	.051
Provide development programmes based on continuous appraisal of performance	99%	97%	100%	100%	1.503	.472
Allocating certain number of hours for development programmes each year	29%	16%	12%	70%	25.631	.000
Provide development programmes before being given salary increments	86%	75%	92%	95%	5.215	.074
Move cross functionally	38%	39%	23%	55%	9.643	.141

Note: $p < 0.05$

Table 7: HR managers' contribution to the strategy process on MD/HRD aspects

Item	Overall <i>Mean</i> (<i>SD</i>)	Local <i>Mean</i> (<i>SD</i>)	Foreign <i>Mean</i> (<i>SD</i>)	Joint venture <i>Mean</i> (<i>SD</i>)	ANOVA	
					F	Sig.
Participate in company decision-making	3.628 (1.27)	3.53 (1.413)	3.65 (1.164)	3.75 (1.208)	.186	.83
Contribute to company decision-making	3.321 (1.156)	3.19 (1.281)	3.42 (1.137)	3.4 (.994)	.355	.702
Accept proposals at the Board Level	3.308 (1.023)	3.16 (1.272)	3.31 (.97)	3.55 (.51)	.909	.407

Note: $p < 0.05$

APPENDIX

Appendix 1: Managerial posts in existence

Post	Overall (n=78)	Local (n=32)	Foreign (n=26)	Joint venture (n=20)
Director(s)	78, 100%	32, 100%	26, 100%	20, 100%
CEO	69, 86%	23, 72%	26, 100%	20, 100%
Heads of Departments/senior managers				
General/Strategic management	78, 100%	32, 100%	16, 62%	19, 95%
Production	78, 100%	32, 100%	26, 100%	20, 100%
Marketing/Merchandising	78, 100%	32, 100%	15, 58%	20, 100%
Accounting & Finance	78, 100%	32, 100%	26, 100%	20, 100%
R&D/Design	22, 28%	2, 06%	5, 19%	15, 75%
HR/Labour relations	78, 100%	32, 100%	26, 100%	20, 100%
Middle level managers				
Middle level managers	78, 100%	32, 100%	26, 100%	20, 100%
Lower level managers				
Lower level managers	78, 100%	32, 100%	26, 100%	20, 100%

Appendix 2: Composition of the management

Post	Local			Foreign			Joint venture		
	L	F	M	L	F	M	L	F	M
Director(s)	100%	--	--	--	100%	--	--	--	100%
CEO	72%	--	--	--	100%	--	70%	30%	--
Heads of Departments/senior managers									
General/Strategic management	100%	--	--	23%	39%	--	95%	--	--
Production	100%	--	--	23%	77%	--	80%	20%	--
Marketing/Merchandising	100%	--	--	--	58%	--	100%	--	--
Accounting & Finance	100%	--	--	19%	81%	--	100%	--	--
R&D/Design	1.3%	1.3%	--	--	19%	--	40%	35%	--
HR/Labour relations	100%	--	--	100%	--	--	100%	--	--
Middle level managers									
Middle level managers	100%	--	--	100%	--	--	100%	--	--
Lower level managers									
Lower level managers	100%	--	--	100%	--	--	100%	--	--

L- Only locals, F- Only foreigners, M- Mix of locals and foreigners